

Regolith Advanced Surface Systems Operations Robot (RASSOR)

Robert P. Mueller
National Aeronautics & Space
Administration (NASA)
M/S: NE-S, Kennedy Space Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-867-2557
rob.mueller@nasa.gov

Rachel E. Cox
National Aeronautics & Space
Administration (NASA)
M/S: NE-S, Kennedy Space Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-861-8325
rachel.cox@nasa.gov

Tom Ebert
National Aeronautics & Space
Administration (NASA)
M/S: NE-S, Kennedy Space Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-867-9261
tom.ebert-1@nasa.gov

Jonathan D. Smith
National Aeronautics & Space
Administration (NASA)
M/S: NE-M, Kennedy Space Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-867-8726
jonathan.d.smith@nasa.gov

Jason M. Schuler
ESC
M/S: ESC-58, Kennedy Space
Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-867-7854
jason.m.schuler@nasa.gov

Andrew J. Nick
ESC
M/S: ESC-58, Kennedy Space
Center
KSC, FL 32899, USA
321-867-4873
andrew.j.nick@nasa.gov

Abstract—Regolith is abundant on extra-terrestrial surfaces and is the source of many resources such as oxygen, hydrogen, titanium, aluminum, iron, silica and other valuable materials, which can be used to make rocket propellant, consumables for life support, radiation protection barrier shields, landing pads, blast protection berms, roads, habitats and other structures and devices. Recent data from the Moon also indicates that there are substantial deposits of water ice in permanently shadowed crater regions and possibly under an over burden of regolith. The key to being able to use this regolith and acquire the resources, is being able to manipulate it with robotic excavation and hauling machinery that can survive and operate in these very extreme extra-terrestrial surface environments.

In addition, the reduced gravity on the Moon, Mars, comets and asteroids poses a significant challenge in that the necessary reaction force for digging cannot be provided by the robot's weight as is typically done on Earth. Space transportation is expensive and limited in capacity, so small, lightweight payloads are desirable, which means large traditional excavation machines are not a viable option.

A novel, compact and lightweight excavation robot prototype for manipulating, excavating, acquiring, hauling and dumping regolith on extra-terrestrial surfaces has been developed and tested. Lessons learned and test results will be presented including digging in a variety of lunar regolith simulant conditions including frozen regolith mixed with water ice

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1. INTRODUCTION

Space resource utilization promises to revolutionize the human condition [1], but the first step in this activity is acquiring the space resources to be used as feedstock. In this case the space resource under consideration is extra-terrestrial regolith, with emphasis on lunar regolith, since it is well characterized from previous missions such as NASA's Apollo program. The lunar regolith consists of approximately 42% oxygen by mass, [2] which can be extracted using chemical engineering methods and then used in space for rocket engine propellant, life support air, water production and usage as a consumable gas [3]. In addition, there are other volatiles present in the lunar regolith such as water, hydrogen, helium, carbon monoxide and helium 3 which are all potentially valuable in a space resource utilization system [4]. Other byproducts of extracting these volatiles are useful metals such as aluminum, iron and titanium.

Terrestrial designs for soil excavation use heavy machines to use their weight and traction as a reaction force to the excavation forces. On extra-terrestrial surfaces, the reduced gravity environment does not provide high weights and the launch costs and packaging constraints of sending such traditional heavy and large excavators into space are prohibitive. Therefore the design of future extra-terrestrial excavators must be re-examined. In addition planetary body regolith such as found on the moon is typically a fine dry mineral based powder that has resulted from billions of years of meteorite impact events. Terrestrial excavation machines operating in sands and similar granular materials often use a bucket wheel design, which is proven and common in the mining industry.

The state of the art and history of extra-terrestrial excavators has been discussed and documented by one of the authors in a previous paper [9], and can be referenced for context.

The RASSOR design represents a ten year design evolution journey which was sponsored by NASA. Initially, in the early 2,000's, the Colorado School of Mines (Dr. Mike Duke et al.) developed a lunar regolith mining prototype concept based on the terrestrial bucket wheel design which then evolved into a bucket ladder design. Meanwhile, Lockheed Martin used the bucket wheel concept to develop the bucket drum [8] lunar excavator prototype. This design was tested on Mauna Kea in Hawaii in tephra volcanic ash. The shortcomings were found to be traction and reaction force. Subsequently, the NASA Kennedy Space Center Surface Systems Office developed the RASSOR prototype in the Granular Mechanics & Regolith Operations (GMRO) lab, by using the bucket drum design in a novel counter-rotating configuration, so that the horizontal excavation forces would cancel each other out, resulting in a lightweight excavation robot that is capable of digging into highly compacted lunar regolith simulants and icy regolith frozen mixtures.

2. REGOLITH EXCAVATION NEEDS

Since typically more than 90% of the mass required for chemical rocket propulsion systems (such as hydrogen-oxygen combustion engines) is propellant [5], the highest priority in space resource utilization is to make and use propellants in-situ. Large mission mass savings will result since the deep gravity well of the Earth, which accounts for 9.3 -10 km/s of delta-velocity to reach low Earth orbit from Kennedy Space Center at an orbital inclination of 28 degrees, can be avoided. The logistics train can also be simplified, and the robustness of a mission can be improved as the crew becomes more self-reliant, without regular critical supply shipments from Earth.

If two NASA Constellation class lunar lander missions are assumed per year, then the oxygen propellant required for a chemical propulsion system is approximately 4 tonnes (t) for a four crew, human class vehicle, resulting in 8 t of oxygen required per year. In addition, 2 t of oxygen would be required per year for life support and fuel cell consumables. Therefore, the regolith required would be proportional to these needs, since the oxygen would be extracted from the regolith. The exact quantities are discussed below and vary based on the chemical process used (1%-28% efficiencies), ranging from hydrogen reduction of regolith to Molten Oxide Electrolysis (MOE) methods, and the possible presence of water ice (5%-10%) at the lunar poles (extracted using water distillation and subsequent solar powered electrolysis). [4]

The Regolith Advanced Surface Systems Operations Robot (RASSOR) project assumed that the near-term missions would be robotic precursor landers with limited total payload masses of less than 500 kg – 1,000 kg. These robotic precursors will prove that regolith excavation and utilization is possible as a technology demonstration. Subsequently, multiple micro-excavators operating in a

swarm can be delivered on small landers and meet total mission requirements in a scalable and affordable fashion.

In this paper a prototype robotic micro-excavator is presented that can meet the requirement of excavating enough regolith feedstock to supply 2.5 tonnes of oxygen per year. To achieve the 10 tonnes of oxygen, four RASSOR micro-excavators would be deployed and operated simultaneously. It is assumed for the purposes of this design, that robotic precursor missions are sent before a human mission, in order to prove that the propellant for a 4 crew Constellation class mission can be reliably produced with robotic methods, to supply propellant for the human crew return lunar ascent stage vehicle propulsion (H₂ fuel & O₂ Oxidizer).

3. RASSOR CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

The nominal mission of RASSOR is a five-year long mining operation to deliver lunar regolith to an oxygen production plant. (The plant itself is outside the scope of this project.) An estimated 255,500 kg of regolith needs to be delivered in order for a chemical In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) plant of approximately 1% efficiency (using a hydrogen reduction process) to produce 2,555 kg of oxygen in that period of time. The rationale for producing 2,555 kg of oxygen and the corresponding bulk excavation mass is explained above based on a reference Constellation class human lunar return architecture. This concept of operations assumes that the RASSOR mission will be deployed at a lunar pole on an "eternal peak of light" to simplify the initial design considerations (thermal and power).

RASSOR will arrive on a small robotic precursor lunar lander and then will deploy itself from an approximately 1-meter-high deck by simply driving off the edge, which avoids the need for ramps or other offloading systems. RASSOR is designed to withstand the impact of the fall, land on any side and right itself if necessary. The excavator will need to drive more quickly than previous space exploration robots in order to meet its mining requirements, so it will be free of hazard avoidance software, which would slow it down. Instead, the landing site will be selected in an area that is as flat as possible, and RASSOR will perform "acrobatics" (the process of using the arms to assume various positions) to handle the obstructions and loose soil it will encounter. It will drive over small rocks and either drive around rocks or use acrobatics to pull itself over larger rocks, furrows or ridgelines. In the event of traction loss, RASSOR can somersault to become unstuck or rise up on its arms and roll on the bucket drums, then lower itself and resume normal driving.

RASSOR will drive at least 100 meters away from the lander to avoid kicking dust up onto the lander's solar panels during mining operations and to provide ample surface regolith. The round trip takes 17 minutes, with RASSOR driving at a speed of at least 20 cm/s. In comparison, the Mars Science Lab rover has a top speed of 4 cm/s. It will collect 20 kg of regolith each trip, making a

total of 12,775 trips per year to meet regolith mining requirements. This amounts to 35 trips per day (24-hour period). If the mobility portion takes 17 minutes and the mining takes 10 minutes, then a 30 minute mining cycle will suffice, and the RASSOR can operate for 17.5 hours per day to achieve its goal of 255,500 kg of regolith mined. It can mine the upper surface layer, or it can also trench to access water ice that may be located a meter or more below the surface. The capability of digging in areas with higher concentrations of ice is being tested and will also possibly have a higher yield of 5.5% water. This will require that RASSOR take very small scoops – more of a shaving action – and would be a much longer operation than digging in drier surface regolith. However, much depends on the characteristics and properties of the icy regolith, which are unknown at this time.

At the end of each mining trip, RASSOR returns to the oxygen production plant near the lander, where it raises itself into a vertical dumping position and reverses rotation of its bucket drums to dump the regolith into a receiving hopper that can be up to a meter high off the ground [6]. The ISRU chemical processing plant will be located on the lander and NASA ISRU field tests in Hawaii have proven that such size hydrogen reduction and regolith driers can be transported by such landers, although flight hardware volume and mass will have to be reduced with further development work. RASSOR is powered by batteries that will be recharged at the lander in between mining treks as required. The concept of operations has factored in 6.5 hours per Earth day for recharging operations.

4. RASSOR GENERATION I REQUIREMENTS

After the needs and concept of operations had been identified the more detailed requirements were written. Some of these requirements are specific about how they shall be met, although, a number of the requirements are meant to bound the problem without forcing a specific design. This is to allow the team to be more creative while still meeting requirements to achieve to overall mission. These bounding requirements fit within the Technology readiness level (TRL) 3: “Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof of concept.” [7]

- RASSOR shall successfully deploy itself from the lander.
- RASSOR shall drive 100 m, excavate, and return to the lander. The distance of 100 m is required to access the designated mining area which is located beyond the lander to provide adequate mining surface area and dust free operations. The lander carries the excavation rover and the ISRU plant.
- RASSOR shall have a maximum mass of 50kg, with a preferred mass of 20kg or less. This mass is constrained by the low payload mass allocation

available on small, affordable robotic precursor missions.

- RASSOR shall mine the top 5 cm of surface regolith for nominal regolith mining operations, since the regolith is known (from Apollo[2]) to be loosely consolidated at these depths and homogenous down to the bedrock.
- RASSOR shall be capable of mining 1 meter deep using a slot dozing trench method, for icy regolith mining and science observations. Recent studies indicate that water ice may be present at depths of more than 30 cm, due to the regolith insulated and stable thermal environment.
- RASSOR shall successfully mine 700 kg of regolith within 24 hours.
- RASSOR shall be equipped with a tele-operation remote vision capability (e.g. one or more cameras).
- RASSOR shall recharge its battery at the lander using a dust tolerant connector.
- RASSOR shall have a minimum lifespan of 5 years, to support a typical Design Reference Architecture (DRA) such as the International Space Exploration Coordination (ISECG), Global Exploration Roadmap (GER) and to be cost effective.
- RASSOR shall have the ability to self-right itself.
- RASSOR shall be tele-operated while it will still offer the option to later add redundancy and autonomy for the driving system.
- RASSOR shall survive the lunar night by attaching to a power source on the lander via an umbilical connection, and sheltering under the lander in a thermal insulation shroud system.
- RASSOR shall have sufficient power storage to execute the baseline concept of operations.
- RASSOR shall have thermal control systems to account for operations in the Lunar Poles day times. The very limited polar Lunar night operations shall be in a hibernation mode.

5. RASSOR GENERATION I: DESIGN SOLUTION

RASSOR uses two bucket drum excavators to accomplish its primary function of collecting and transporting regolith. A bucket drum excavator is a novel device that excavates, stores and dumps regolith. Lockheed Martin Space Systems, Denver (under a contract from NASA) developed the first bucket drum for use on a small robotic excavator [8]. The Granular Mechanics & Regolith Operations (GMRO) Lab at NASA Kennedy Space Center has developed a novel

application of the bucket drum concept by employing two counter rotating bucket drums in a robotic platform that has advanced positioning and posing capabilities.

The main advantages of a bucket drum are that the excavation scoops are small and staggered so that at any given time only one or two are engaged in the regolith, thereby keeping the excavation forces low, and the regolith collected becomes trapped inside the drum due to a set of baffles until the direction of rotation is reversed. This approach completely eliminates the need to have a separate regolith storage and dump bin. The bucket drums used on RASSOR each consist of 5 segments with 3 scoops per segment (see figure 1). Each bucket drum is designed to collect and hold 10 kg of regolith when 60% full. They have scoop openings that can accommodate rocks up to 5 cm in diameter. These rocks may be excluded through a grating or other system in the future.

Aluminum sheet metal was used to construct the scoops and baffles which were placed around plates that divide the segments. Five aluminum rods with tapped ends run the length of the bucket drum and attach to the end-caps, compressing the segments together. The scoops on the bucket drums also have stainless steel removable cutting edges that are riveted on. The sheet metal approach kept the mass of the bucket drums to about 7 kg each.

Figure 1 - Bucket drum without end cap to show baffles.

RASSOR's solution to the issue of excavation with low vehicle mass and traction (especially in an extra-terrestrial environment) is to excavate with both bucket drums at the same time while rotating them in opposite directions. This technique counters the horizontal excavation loads of one bucket drum with the other.

The height of the bucket drums with respect to the ground plane needs to be actuated in order to engage the soil and control the cutting depth of the scoops. RASSOR accomplishes this by placing the bucket drums on the ends of single degree-of-freedom arms (see figure 2). Each arm is

driven at a rotational joint on the RASSOR chassis and houses the motor and gearbox for the bucket drum rotation. The bucket drum rotation motor and gearbox are mounted inside the structure of the arm, and a drive shaft transfers the torque from the gearbox output to a bevel gear pair, which in turn drives the bucket drum (see figure 3). Inside the RASSOR chassis, a motor, planetary gearbox, and worm gear system is used to drive the arm rotation.

Figure 2 – RASSOR field test in October 2012.

The arms were also designed to perform acrobatics as a useful mobility feature. Using the dual arm configuration, the vehicle is able to right itself if flipped over, climb over obstacles much taller than the tread height, dump regolith at heights taller than one arm length, and stand the chassis up to clean out debris from the tracks (see figure 4).

The mobility system on RASSOR was also designed to be very simple as the primary goal of this version is to prove the concept of low reaction force dual bucket drum excavation. To that end, the mobility system is a tank tread design that was initially modeled from similarly-sized commercially available drive trains. During testing, however, it was observed that the fine particles would get caught between the treads and the drive pulleys, causing the treads to jam up or track off the pulleys. To fix this, new drive pulleys were designed that have large openings between the teeth so that the soil can clear out from treads.

Figure 3 – A motor, gearbox, and bevel gear drive system turns each bucket drum.

The loose and compacted properties of lunar regolith provide unique mobility challenges due to the loss of traction experienced once the regolith is sheared. The choice of tracks versus wheels is being actively studied and traded against the RASSOR requirements. Each approach has distinct advantages, and this RASSOR prototype has revealed that tracks are much more complex than wheels in the finely powdered lunar regolith simulant.

Figure 4 – Clockwise from top left: RASSOR self-righting (shown just before tumbling over its left drum); climbing over an obstacle much taller than its tracks; positioning to dump its left bucket drum, also called the “Z” position; and raising its chassis (iron cross position) to spin the tracks and free them of debris.

RASSOR is controlled via remote driver station software on a laptop. The driver station shows the display from the cameras and reads inputs from a gamepad controller. High level control commands are then sent to the vehicle via a wireless radio. An Ethernet to CAN converter onboard the vehicle then decodes the Ethernet commands and sends the appropriate CANopen commands to the motor controllers. All of the actuators on RASSOR are controlled using Elmo Motion Control motor controllers. Each motor is equipped

with an incremental encoder for closed loop velocity control. An axis video encoder converts analog video from two cameras and streams them back on the wireless Ethernet network. Two 12V 19AH lithium iron phosphate batteries are wired in series to power the vehicle.

6. TEST RESULTS

RASSOR was tested in sand, KSC crawler-way fines (crushed river rocks), and lunar regolith simulant Black Point -1 (BP-1). Fine sand is a readily abundant but low-fidelity simulant, which was suitable for early testing such as demonstrating RASSOR's ability to drive, dig and assume acrobatics positions (see figure 5).

Figure 5 – RASSOR in the “Z” position demonstrating its ability to dump sand.

The crawler-way fines compacted well, which provided a way to test RASSOR's ability to overcome higher excavation forces. RASSOR was able to dig successfully, as long as the digging depth was very shallow (less than a centimeter), which meant it took much longer to fill the bucket drums. The crawler-way fines also contained a lot of rocks and gravel, which tended to get caught between the wheels and the tracks and caused much trouble during testing, especially during counter-steering. (See figure 10 in the Lessons Learned section). RASSOR also demonstrated that it was able to climb a 20 degree slope, turn, and drive laterally. While it failed to climb straight up a steeper 30 degree slope, this was because the crawler fines were in a loosely piled mound that sheared and avalanched under RASSOR's weight and caused it to slide backwards. It is expected that RASSOR would have succeeded if the hill was more compact, and further testing will be performed to resolve this. In addition, the bucket drum scoops may be used as a “climbing piton” device used for controlled ascending and descending, and this hypothesis will also be tested in the future.

Figure 6 – Driving up a 20 degree slope of loose crawler-way fines.

The BP-1 simulant had the highest lunar simulant fidelity but was only available in one small outdoor test bin. RASSOR was able to successfully drive, perform acrobatics, dig loose surface regolith, and trench. Measurements were taken that confirmed the bucket drums were able to collect not only 10 kg of regolith each, as designed, but upwards of 14.5 kg. Current draw was measured and recorded for different activities (see fig. 8.). RASSOR pulled 3 to 5 amps while driving; 8 to 10 amps while raising its chassis into the iron cross position; 3 to 4 amps while lowering the chassis back down; and 2 amps during shallow mining. Temperature was also measured and exceeded 150 degrees F after less than two hours of outdoors testing (see fig. 9). This was of concern because the motor controllers have a rated maximum operating temperature of 180 degrees F, so temperature will continue to be monitored, particularly when testing outdoors in the heat. Future versions of RASSOR will include provisions for cooling and will provide traceability to lunar conditions with a suitably sized radiator on the top surface.

RASSOR was also tested in BP-1 using a setup that off-loaded 5/6th of its weight to simulate lunar gravity. One bucket drum was lowered into the simulant to mine, and the excavation reaction forces were greater than the traction, which translated the vehicle without excavating soil. When the second drum was lowered, RASSOR stopped sliding and both drums began to collect soil, thereby demonstrating the efficacy of dual counter-rotating bucket drum system. It also appeared that vertical reaction forces were low enough not to influence RASSOR's digging, and there are future test plans to quantify them.

RASSOR was tested again with the gravity off-loader, this time in icy regolith, which was a mixture of BP-1 with 10% water by weight, that was compacted and cryogenically frozen to 83K using liquid nitrogen. RASSOR demonstrated it was able to mine, with the advantage that frozen BP-1 was very brittle and able to be broken up. A shortcoming of the test, however, was that it was performed outside in the summer, where the air temperature exceeded 90 degrees F and continually warmed the test bed. Prior lab tests showed the BP-1 stayed frozen at the core for an hour. But during testing it appeared that the outer layer was easier

for RASSOR to scrape off until it hit a harder, more frozen layer, which then subsequently warmed. For future tests, it would be desirable to have liquid nitrogen keeping the regolith frozen during testing, which would involve a more complex test setup but have higher fidelity.

Figure 7 – RASSOR testing using gravity off-loader and icy BP-1

Fig. 8 – Current draw during two hours of testing RASSOR’s driving, mining, and acrobatics capabilities. Lower current draw (i.e. 0 to 15 mins) corresponds with driving or light mining; higher current draw (i.e. 85 to 100 mins) corresponds with multiple operations run simultaneously, such as driving and trenching.

Figure 9 – RASSOR internal temperature during two hours of testing. Sharp drops in temperature correspond to shutting RASSOR off for periods of time, during which data was not recorded.

7. LESSONS LEARNED AND GOOD PRACTICES

Improvements to the design of RASSOR were found during fabrication, assembly, and testing. The three sections below summarize the lessons learned during these stages.

Fabrication

One improvement learned from the fabrication process is to design for minimized part count rather than ease of

fabrication. In many cases, it may actually be quicker to machine a complicated part on a multi-axis CNC rather than machine and assemble several parts on a simpler machine, such as a water-jet cutter. This would also avoid problems later on during assembly, as those multiple parts may need to be aligned very closely to function properly. A single piece part avoids stacked tolerances.

Assembly

With a tight requirement on size and weight, it was beneficial to pack hardware into the chassis as tightly as possible. This resulted in limiting the accessibility of many components during assembly and maintenance. As more components of the system were tested, it was necessary to remove some of them to fix or adjust certain aspects. If the whole robot had to be disassembled to get to the drive wheel motor, for example, it became very time consuming and impractical. Another problem with taking components apart and putting them back together many times is that some may actually wear out in ways that wouldn't happen during normal robot operations.

Another point is to ensure that wiring has been well-accounted for. Designers will often create CAD models that neglect the wires connecting all the motors, controllers, cameras, etc., which makes it hard to envision the final setup. Wires may run very close to open gears and shafts and could get caught as the rover moves over rough terrain. Additionally, wires may block access to components that need to be adjusted in place, such as the tensioner for a chain or belt. In the case of RASSOR, these problems were mitigated after final assembly of the robot, but in the future, including them in the model would provide better results.

Testing

With a complex design, the testing phase will typically reveal the most areas in need of improvement. This was certainly the case with RASSOR.

The first subsystem that required many adjustments were the tracks. It turned out to be very challenging to design a track drive system that could work in a variety of soils analogous to lunar regolith. Initial tests in sand exposed the clogging problem, where regolith particles accumulated between the wheels and the tracks, causing the track to lose tooth engagement and slip off the wheel. This was remedied by redesigning open wheels that allowed the dirt to flow out towards the hub as the wheels turned. This solved the clogging issue for most types of soft and hard soil, except for those like the crawlerway fines with larger size rocks that could still get wedged in the wheel (fig 10).

Figure 10 – Crawler-way gravel lodged in the track, which pushed up against the arm crossbar and locked up the drive system.

Another improvement was to exchange an all-rubber belt material with one that encompassed stainless steel wire ropes running continuously through it. This corrected a belt stretch issue that had been contributing to the belt coming off the wheels when clogged. That issue was exaggerated at elevated temperatures due to the rubber softening. It should be pointed out the on the moon the opposite issue would occur where the rubber would lose its flexibility. However, rubber would not be used on the moon; but as a terrestrial analog it was acceptable in this prototype. The experience from testing with tracks has indicated that the next generation RASSOR prototype should use wheels instead of tracks to simplify operations and avoid the regolith induced problems. The trade-off of tracks versus wheels corresponds directly to traction needs and if RASSOR can drive out of a 20 degree incline trench ramp with wheels, then this could be the preferred solution due to the lower mass and higher reliability of a wheeled system. Future work will address this design detail.

Initial testing of the arms revealed that the chain connecting two gearboxes in series worked as designed in one direction, but skipped teeth under load in the other direction. This was due to the entrance angle of the chain onto the drive sprocket not being equal in both directions. The issue was solved by tightening the chain, which had to be done repeatedly, as the chain stretches. With this improvement in place, the next issue that occurred was too much friction between gears on a custom gearbox housing using off-the-shelf gears. The root of this problem was a misalignment between the gears caused by tolerance stacking among the multiple parts comprising the gearbox housing.

A general improvement to be made during the testing phase is to test subsystems that appear multiple times on a single unit prior to integration. This will allow adjustments to be made to the single assembly rather than all copies at once. This was most apparent on the arm mechanism, which utilized four identical gear trains that underwent several iterations. The speed at which iterations were made would

have increased if updates had been made to a single unit only.

A set of encoders was linked to the output of the motor through a set of spur gears. The backlash of the spur gears coupled with some wobble in the associated ball bearings was enough to confuse the motor controllers and cause the motors to stop intermittently. The last set of encoders was attached directly to the output shaft of the motor, which was optimal. However, even this setup needed one improvement primarily because of the way the encoder wheel was designed. The plastic encoder wheel was intended to simply press-fit onto a shaft, which in RASSOR's case was smooth and had high accelerations and decelerations. This resulted in the encoder coming loose. Knurling the surface of the shaft and using an adhesive solved this negative. It is highly recommended to use encoders with positive locking encoder wheels directly on the motor output to avoid this issue.

The remaining lessons learned do not suggest hardware changes, but rather refinements and proper implementation of the operations concept. The original concept of the counter-rotating bucket drums was to make shallow skim cuts off the soil surface and drive while digging to fill up the scoops. In practice, this turned out to be difficult due to the purely manual control that required constant driver input. If there was any initial unevenness in the soil surface, those bumps would make the rover move off level as it drove forward, which meant one drum would be raised off the ground while the other would be driven deeper into the soil. This created more unevenness for the next time the rover would make another pass. Another unintended side effect of the deep cut is that under some soil conditions the scoops could get clogged with compacted regolith, and therefore become ineffective (fig. 11). On the moon, low gravity, electrostatic forces, Van der Waal forces, and high friction forces between the particles could create a similar situation whereby cohesion of the granular material is increased, causing similar bridging and clogging. This will be addressed in future designs by opening the size of the scoop opening to prevent bridging or by vibrating the drum to free the particles.

Figure 11 – Scoop clogged with damp sand.

The digging depth problems could be mitigated by automating (with scripting) the skim cut operations so that the driver would not need to try to adjust the arms constantly to keep them level even as the rover chassis bounced. Driving very slowly while digging would allow the arms to keep up with the moving chassis in order to take even, shallow cuts. The same scripting approach should be taken for the acrobatics moves in order to smooth out the loads during those maneuvers.

Lastly, testing in icy regolith required some changes in the digging approach. It seems to be more effective to first break up the hard, icy soil and then scoop up what has been broken loose. A faster drum rotation will help the breaking up step, while the slower drum rotation will then be used to pick up the soil. Improvements in the cutting edge of each scoop, such as serrations or sharp pick ahead of the cutting edge will also help the rover perform better while digging icy regolith.

8. SUMMARY

A novel, compact and lightweight excavation robot prototype for manipulating, excavating, acquiring, hauling and dumping regolith on extra-terrestrial surfaces has been developed and tested at the NASA, Kennedy Space Center. Lessons learned and test results have been presented in this paper, including results from digging in a variety of lunar regolith simulant conditions as well as frozen regolith mixed with water ice.

This prototyping effort has shown promising results and proven the concept of using counter rotating bucket drums as an effective method of manipulating regolith in a load, haul and dump scenario, to produce a micro-excavator system that can be delivered to the moon and other extra-terrestrial bodies on small robotic landers. This method successfully mitigates the problem of only having low digging reaction forces available in low gravity environments, which is a major challenge when using traditional excavation methods, such as those used on Earth.

The lessons learned have been valuable and the testing has also revealed opportunities for improving the design and operations. A second generation RASSOR will be designed, fabricated and tested to take advantage of these opportunities. Eventually, it is hoped that a swarm of RASSOR's will operate on the moon and other extra-terrestrial bodies to enable regolith mining for space resource utilization.

REFERENCES

[1] Metzger, P.T., Muscatello, A., Mueller, R.P., and Mantovani, J. "Affordable, rapid bootstrapping of space industry and solar system civilization", (2012) Accepted to be published in the American Society of Civil Engineers, Journal of Aerospace Engineering.

[2] Schmitt, Jack. *Lunar sourcebook: A user's guide to the Moon*. Eds. Grant Heiken, David Vaniman, and Bevan M. French. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

[3] Sanders, Gerald B., and William E. Larson. "Progress Made in Lunar In Situ Resource Utilization under NASA's Exploration Technology and Development Program." *Journal of Aerospace Engineering* 1 (2012): 157.

[4] Colaprete, A., Schultz, P., Heldmann, J., Wooden, D., Shirley, M., Ennico, K., & Sollitt, L. (2010). Detection of water in the LCROSS ejecta plume. *Science*, 330(6003), 463-468.

[5] Holt, James B., and Timothy S. Monk. "Propellant Mass Fraction Calculation Methodology for Launch Vehicles." (2009).

[6] Robert P. Mueller and Ivan Townsend, "Lunar Regolith Simulant Feed System for a Hydrogen Reduction Reactor System", 47th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting, Orlando, FL, Jan. 2009.

[7] "Technology Readiness Assessment (TRA) Guidance". United States Department of Defense. April 2011.

[8] Clark, D., R. Patterson, and D. Wurts. "A novel approach to planetary regolith collection: the bucket drum soil excavator." *AIAA Space 2009 Conference & Exposition*. 2009.

[9] Mueller, Robert P., and Paul J. Van Susante. "A Review of Extra-Terrestrial Mining Robot Concepts." *Earth and Space 2012, Construction, and Operations in Challenging Environments*. ASCE, 2011.

Biographies

Robert P. Mueller received a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Miami, Coral Gables, a Master of Space Systems Engineering from the Technical University of Delft, Netherlands and a Master in Business Administration from the Florida Institute of Technology in Melbourne. He has been with NASA for more than 24 years where he has had numerous positions in the Space Shuttle, International Space Station, X-33, Orbital Space Plane and Constellation Programs. Most recently he was the Chief of the Kennedy Space Center (KSC) Surface Systems Office, and currently he is the Lunar Destination Co-Lead on the NASA Human Spaceflight Architecture Team (HAT) as well as the KSC lead for Human Robotic Systems. Mr. Mueller is the co-founder and Head Judge for the NASA Lunabotics Mining Competition for universities and he is a member of the American Institute of Aeronautics & Astronautics (AIAA) and the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE).

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Rachel E. Cox received a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering in 2001 from the University of Louisville in Louisville, Kentucky. She has been with NASA for one year as an aerospace technologist developing technologies for robotically mining lunar and other planetary surfaces.

Tom Ebert received a B.S. and M.S. in Aerospace Engineering from Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University in Daytona Beach, FL. He has been with NASA since 2008, where he began work in the Structural Analysis branch and is currently working in the Mechanisms Design branch. He is the lead design engineer for multiple launch equipment systems to be used for NASA's SLS vehicle. He is also supporting the KSC Human Robotics Systems project in the KSC Surface Systems Office by designing and testing several systems which may be deployed on the moon. Outside of work, he is currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Mechanical Engineering with a concentration on robotics from the Florida Institute of Technology.

Jason M. Schuler received a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from Florida Institute of Technology in 2007. He has been a contractor for NASA at the Kennedy Space Center for 5 years. Jason supports the NE-S office at KSC developing robotic technology and excavation tools for the moon and Mars. He has designed hardware for the SEV and ATHLETE rovers at JSC and JPL. In his personal time Jason is also heavily involved with FIRST robotics and educational outreach.

Jonathan D. Smith received a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from The University of North Florida in 2009. He has been with NASA Kennedy Space Center for 3 years. Currently he is working in the KSC Surface System Office, NE-S. Prior to NE-S he worked in the KSC Institutional Engineering Safety division where he led teams to define hazardous operations and implemented mitigating controls for cryogenics as well as many other tests and operations. Currently within NE-S he is working on percussive excavation technology to reduce excavation forces for low mass excavators in reduced gravity. He also is on a design team that is developing zero net reaction force excavating technology for micro

excavators in reduced and micro gravity.

***Andrew J. Nick** received a B.S in Mechanical Engineering from The Florida Institute of Technology in 2007. For the past 5 years he has been a contractor for NASA at the Kennedy Space Center, supporting the KSC Surface Systems Office developing excavation tools and*

robotic technology for the Moon and Mars. He has designed hardware for the ATHLETE and SEV rovers at JPL and JSC.

